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APPLYING INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW AND *JUS AD BELLUM* TO USES OF THE ELECTROMAGNETIC SPECTRUM IN OUTER SPACE

ADINA SAKURA DARBYSHIRE¹

ABSTRACT

The electromagnetic spectrum (EMS) in outer space, in particular, the radio frequency spectrum, which forms a part of the EMS, serves a crucial function for transmitting signals between satellites in orbit and ground stations on Earth for the supply of essential services. For example, satellites rely upon the EMS to monitor natural disasters, track the spread of diseases, and provide navigation services for emergency personnel. For the purposes of this paper, such uses of the EMS in outer space shall be referred to as ‘constructive’ uses.

The EMS can also be utilised for ‘obstructive’ uses such as temporarily interfering with or manipulating satellite signals (i.e., jamming and spoofing) and ‘destructive’ uses such as permanently damaging satellites and even terrestrial electronics (e.g., through directed energy systems). The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine the constructive uses, thereby posing risks to human life and well-being. As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks.

This paper adopts a human-centred approach to examining the international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, as a means of regulating and protecting satellite systems, their constructive uses, and the lives that they support. Further, this paper identifies legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities in the application of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses as areas requiring further research and policy discussions.

KEYWORDS: International Space Law, *Jus ad Bellum*, Space Security, Electromagnetic Spectrum, Electromagnetic Warfare.

¹ Space Court Foundation Intern; adina.darbyshire@spacecourtfoundation.org

1. INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic spectrum (EMS) refers to “the entire range of wavelengths or frequencies of electromagnetic radiation [...]”.² The radio frequency (RF) spectrum lies at the low-energy end of the EMS, with the longest wavelengths and lowest frequencies, making it suitable for transmitting signals between ground stations on Earth and satellites in outer space.³ Thus, the EMS is integral for satellite systems and their ‘constructive’ uses, including telecommunications, navigation, and Earth observation (EO),⁴ upon which lives increasingly depend. By way of illustration, satellites offering telecommunications and navigation services allow persons in need of urgent assistance to contact emergency services and for emergency personnel to locate them. Further, EO satellites are used to monitor and support the management of, *inter alia*, natural disasters, climate change, armed conflicts, agriculture and food stocks, disease epidemiology, watercourses, and the weather.⁵

At the same time, the EMS can be utilised for ‘obstructive’ uses by interfering with satellite signals (“jamming”) or mimicking satellite signals to deceive the target into accepting false signals as legitimate (“spoofing”).⁶ The EMS can also be harnessed for ‘destructive’ uses using directed energy weapons (DEWs) such as high-energy lasers, high-powered microwave weapons, and electromagnetic pulse (EMP) weapons.⁷ An EMP refers to a burst of electromagnetic energy capable of damaging satellites, causing blackouts, and disabling critical infrastructure on Earth, whether generated artificially by a DEW or nuclear detonation, or occurring naturally as a result of a geomagnetic storm.⁸ DEWs at low levels of power may temporarily interfere with rather than permanently destroy satellites, in which case, they would constitute obstructive uses.⁹

The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine satellite systems and their constructive uses, with flow-on effects for individuals, economies, and the environment. Consider the events of 19 July 2024 when the world went dark. An error by the cybersecurity firm CrowdStrike disabled 8.5 million Windows computers, which, in effect, grounded planes, prevented patients from receiving medical attention, and

² Merriam-Webster. (n.d.). *Electromagnetic spectrum*. Merriam-Webster. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/electromagnetic%20spectrum>

³ Science Mission Directorate. (2010). *Radio Waves*. Science Mission Directorate, National Aeronautics and Space Administration. http://science.nasa.gov/ems/05_radiowaves; National Frequency Agency. (n.d.). *What is the frequency spectrum?* National Frequency Agency, Government of France. <https://www.anfr.fr/en/about-the-anfr/what-is-the-frequency-spectrum>;

National Aeronautics and Space Administration. (2025, February 5). *State-of-the-Art of Small Spacecraft Technology*. National Aeronautics and Space Administration. <https://www.nasa.gov/smallsat-institute/sst-soa/soa-communications/>

⁴ See, for example, Eurisy. (n.d.). *Satellite Applications*. Eurisy. <https://www.eurisy.eu/satellite-applications/>; UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (n.d.). *Benefits of Space for Humankind*. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/benefits-of-space/benefits.html>

⁵ Eurisy, *supra* note 4; UNOOSA, *supra* note 4.

⁶ Way, T. (2019, October 28). *Counterspace Weapons 101*. Center for Strategic & International Studies. <https://aerospace.csis.org/aerospace101/counterspace-weapons-101/>

⁷ Beard, J., & Stephens, D. (Eds.). (2024). *The Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations*. Oxford University Press. (“Woomera Manual”) (p. 208); Grand-Clément, S. (2022, May 12). *Directed Energy Weapons: A New Look at an ‘Old’ Technology*. The United Nations Institute for Disarmament Research. <https://unidir.org/directed-energy-weapons-a-new-look-at-an-old-technology/>

⁸ Luzetsky, H. R. (2025, June 5). *EMP Hardening of Critical Infrastructure*. Homeland Defense & Security Information Analysis Center (HDIAC), U.S. Department of Defense. <https://hdiac.dtic.mil/articles/emp-hardening-of-critical-infrastructure/>

⁹ U.S. Government Accountability Office. (May 25, 2023). *Science & Tech Spotlight: Directed Energy Weapons*. U.S. Government Accountability Office. <https://www.gao.gov/products/gao-23-106717>; Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 209).

cost US Fortune 500 companies an estimated US\$5.4 billion in losses.¹⁰ Not only could similar flow-on effects potentially occur due to a widespread disruption to satellites or a terrestrial power outage, but there could also be environmental implications given the role of EO satellites in climate change monitoring. In the case of CrowdStrike, 97% of computers were reportedly restored after one week,¹¹ whereas it has been estimated that a severe geomagnetic storm (known as a Carrington event) could result in a power outage lasting up to two years.¹² Whether an EMP occurs due to space weather or DEWs, the consequences of such a prolonged power outage could be devastating.

While all such effects warrant examination, this paper takes a human-centred approach, focusing on risks to human life and well-being. This paper examines the application of the international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, to the obstructive and destructive uses, with an emphasis on the regulation of second- and third-order risks (in decreasing order of directness). Less emphasis will be accorded to first-order risks, which refer to risks of direct harm to individuals (e.g., adverse health impacts of electromagnetic radiation for individuals on Earth or astronauts and space tourists in outer space), given their relative indeterminacy.

Second-order risks refer to risks of harm to essential services or critical infrastructure on Earth upon which lives depend, thereby posing a threat to individuals. Namely, an EMP-induced power outage would threaten basic human needs, as power is critical for refrigerating and transporting food, electric pumps and treatment facilities ensuring the supply of water, and the storage of medications and life-sustaining devices (e.g., ventilators).¹³ Given such risks, the National Coordinating Center for Communications (NCC) of the US has published critical infrastructure resilience guidelines in the event of an EMP.¹⁴ These guidelines recognise that, for certain infrastructure, an EMP-induced power outage of a few hours, minutes, or even seconds could threaten human life (e.g., nuclear power plant controls).¹⁵

Third-order risks refer to risks of harm to satellite systems, which in turn can threaten essential services or critical infrastructure on Earth, thereby posing a threat to individuals. The obstructive and destructive uses can disable satellites and render their constructive uses unavailable, weakening systems on Earth designed to protect against, *inter alia*, natural disasters, food shortages, the spread of disease, and lack of clean water. For example, the Iran Meteorological Organization reportedly cited the jamming of satellite signals as a reason for its inability to “provide sufficient warning to Tehran citizens ahead of a June 12, 2014 sandstorm that claimed five lives and injured 44 Tehran citizens [...]”.¹⁶ Further, according to a 2026 survey by the Royal Institute of Navigation of at least 271 respondents from the maritime sector, 7% and

¹⁰ Livesay, B., & Wilson, C. (Eds.). (2024, September 24). 'Deeply sorry,' CrowdStrike boss apologises for global IT outage. BBC. <https://www.bbc.com/news/live/ckgnxd7d26gt>

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² Lloyds. (2013). *Solar Storm Risk to the North American Electric Grid*. Lloyd's. <https://assets.lloyds.com/assets/pdf-solar-storm-risk-to-the-north-american-electric-grid/1/pdf-Solar-Storm-Risk-to-the-North-American-Electric-Grid.pdf> (p. 16).

¹³ See, for example, National Coordinating Center for Communications (NCC). (2019, February 5). *Electromagnetic Pulse (EMP) Protection and Resilience Guidelines for Critical Infrastructure and Equipment*. NCC, U.S. Department of Homeland Security. https://www.cisa.gov/sites/default/files/publications/19_0307_CISA_EMP-Protection-Resilience-Guidelines.pdf; G Granholm, F. Tin, D., & Ciotton, G. R. (2023). Critical Energy Infrastructure and Health: How Loss of Power May Kill. *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine*, 38(2), 279–280. doi:10.1017/S1049023X23000274; U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). (2019, June). *Power Resilience: Guide for Water and Wastewater Utilities*. EPA. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2016-03/documents/160212-powerresiliencguide508.pdf>

¹⁴ NCC, *supra* note 13.

¹⁵ *Ibid* (pp. iii–iv).

¹⁶ Center for Human Rights in Iran. (2014, July 23). *Jamming of Satellite Broadcast Signals Prevented Ability to See Fatal Sandstorm Coming*. Center for Human Rights in Iran. <https://iranhumanrights.org/2014/07/jamming-satellite/>

11% experienced incorrect time displays on Safety of Life at Sea (SOLAS) and Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS) equipment, respectively, during a jamming or spoofing attack against the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS).¹⁷ This indicates a risk that such equipment would transmit incorrect location data in an emergency.¹⁸

As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks. Identifying legal lacunae in the application of international law, including the international space law framework, is particularly salient for the obstructive and destructive uses, whose non-kinetic nature and cascading effects do not necessarily align with traditional legal conceptions. Accordingly, Section 2 will examine the applicability of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses.

2. APPLICABILITY OF THE INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW FRAMEWORK

The Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, Including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies (“Outer Space Treaty” or “OST”) lies at the heart of international space law. As the long title indicates, the OST applies to the “exploration and use” of “outer space”.¹⁹ Before proceeding to the question of *how* the international space law framework applies to the obstructive and destructive uses (as considered in Section 3), it is necessary to assess whether such uses fall within the scope of this language, such that the OST would apply.

Looking first at the meaning of “outer space”, this can be characterised as an area beyond 100 km above mean sea level (i.e., Kármán line).²⁰ Based on a strict spatialist approach (and a tentative presumption that the Kármán line applies), the applicability of the OST would hinge on whether the obstructive and destructive uses occur above the Kármán line. As satellites maintain a physical presence in orbit, it is generally uncontested that satellite systems are governed by international space law, even if ground stations are on Earth. Meanwhile, obstructive and destructive uses targeting satellite signals rely on the delivery of energy rather than mass, and may originate from aircraft or ground stations, thereby only having a physical presence below the Kármán line. Accordingly, the extent to which obstructive and destructive uses could be characterised as existing in “outer space” is uncertain. For example, international space law may apply to space-based DEWs or satellite-to-satellite jamming but have limited application to ground-based DEWs targeting satellites or to jamming attacks against satellite signals occurring on Earth.

According to a functionalist approach to the meaning of “outer space”, the determinative factor is whether an activity is space-related, so it is arguable that obstructive and destructive uses are governed by international space law insofar as these affect satellite systems. This is consistent with the *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (“Tallinn Manual”), a non-binding manual prepared by leading international law practitioners and scholars on cyber operations, which provides that “[a]ctivities on the earth also qualify as space activities when they involve activities, or otherwise achieve

¹⁷ Royal Institute of Navigation (January 2026). *Impacts of GNSS Interference on Maritime Safety: A special report by the RIN Maritime GNSS Interference Working Group*. https://rin.org.uk/page/RIN_Maritime_Report (pp. 34–35).

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Treaty on Principles Governing the Activities of States in the Exploration and Use of Outer Space, including the Moon and Other Celestial Bodies*, opened for signature January 27 1967, 610 UNTS 205 (entered into force October 10 1967) (“Outer Space Treaty”) (art. XIII).

²⁰ Ortega, A. A., & Samson, V. (Eds.). (2023). *A Lexicon for Outer Space Security* (p. 34). UN Institute of Disarmament Research (UNIDIR). <https://doi.org/10.37559/WMD/23/Space/05>

effects, in outer space [...]”²¹ However, the Tallinn Manual also provides that the applicability of space law is limited in respect of satellite-to-Earth cyber communications, which constitute “space-enabled cyber operations” as distinguished from “cyber-enabled space operations”.²² By analogy, obstructive uses occurring entirely on Earth may constitute space-enabled electromagnetic operations as distinguished from EMS-enabled counter-space operations, limiting the application of space law. Thus, the precise extent to which obstructive and destructive uses constitute space activities for the purposes of the OST remains unclear and requires case-by-case assessments, which are further complicated by ongoing debates on the definition and delimitation of outer space.²³

Turning to the meaning of “exploration and use”, these terms have generally been interpreted disjointly rather than conjointly, such that it is sufficient that an obstructive or destructive use constitutes a “use” and not an “exploration” for the OST to apply.²⁴ Gorove posits that a “use” would likely exclude “the use of the sunrays for everyday seeing”, but include “the more specific or direct use of the sun's energy in outer space, especially in spatial travel or experiments, such as for propulsion, heating, etc. [...]”²⁵ By analogy, the RF spectrum is harnessed by – and in the case of naturally-occurring EMPs, can interfere with – satellite systems (i.e., passive use), whereas it can also enable satellite systems to serve specific applications, or conversely, intentionally disable or destroy those satellite systems (i.e., active use). Accordingly, the obstructive and destructive uses – which represent active rather than passive uses of the EMS – would likely constitute a “use”. As the freedom of States to use outer space is subject to duties (e.g., a “use” must be “carried out for the benefit and in the interests of all countries”),²⁶ it is material to distinguish between active and passive uses such that only the former is subject to such duties. Otherwise, States would be responsible for ensuring the EMS benefits all countries in its natural, passive state.²⁷

While recognising that not all obstructive and destructive uses may qualify as space activities and underlining the need to clarify doctrinal ambiguities concerning the meaning of “outer space”, Section 3 will proceed on the tentative presumption that all such “uses” are governed by international space law. Section 3 will analyse the ways in which the international space law framework may limit the freedom of use of outer space in cases involving the obstructive and destructive uses, with a view to assessing the regulation of resulting second- and third-order risks to human life and well-being.

²¹ Schmitt, M. N. (2017). *Tallinn Manual 2.0 on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Operations* (2nd ed.) Cambridge: Cambridge University Press (“Tallinn Manual”) (p. 272).

²² Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 270).

²³ See, for example, UN Office for Outer Space Affairs (UNOOSA). (n.d.). *Working Group on the Definition and Delimitation of Outer Space of the Legal Subcommittee*. UNOOSA. <https://www.unoosa.org/oosa/en/ourwork/copuos/lsc/ddos/index.html>

²⁴ Leclerc, T (Ed.). (2024, January 9). *Space Law: Legal Framework for Space Activities*. John Wiley & Sons (p. 69); Gorove, S. (1971, January). Freedom of Exploration and Use in the Outer Space Treaty: A Textual Analysis and Interpretation. *Denver Journal of International Law & Policy*, 1(1), 93–107. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2191&&context=djilp> (p. 97).

²⁵ Gorove, *supra* note 24 (p. 99).

²⁶ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. I).

²⁷ While legal frameworks other than international space law and *jus ad bellum* exceed the scope of this paper, it is notable that frameworks such as international environmental law could potentially be applied to bolster protections of outer space and its natural resources, including the EMS, independently of its use.

3. HOW THE INTERNATIONAL SPACE LAW FRAMEWORK APPLIES

3.1. Peaceful Purposes

The OST provides that “[t]he moon and other celestial bodies shall be used [...] exclusively for peaceful purposes”.²⁸ Together with the preamble and other operative provisions referring to “the peaceful exploration and use of outer space”, this article can be interpreted without limitation to celestial bodies, extending to void space.²⁹ States have generally interpreted “peaceful” to mean “non-military” or “non-aggressive”. If the former interpretation were accepted, it would follow that obstructive or destructive uses carried out by military actors are unlawful, but State practice favours the latter.³⁰

Where “peaceful” is interpreted as “non-aggressive”, obstructive and destructive uses are permissible insofar as these do not constitute prohibited uses of force, notwithstanding possible violations of other rules of general international law (e.g., non-intervention principle, laws of State responsibility). Laws concerning the use of force form part of the *jus ad bellum* regime developed under the UN Charter. As Article III of the OST expressly provides that the use of outer space shall be in accordance with the UN Charter, recourse thereto also falls within the international space law framework. Thus, the extent to which the “peaceful purposes” requirement limits the obstructive and destructive uses hinges on the relevant rules of the UN Charter.

It is notable, however, that the Tallinn Manual has referred to a “controversy” as to whether cyber activities not meeting the threshold of a use of force could nonetheless be prohibited as violating the “peaceful purposes” requirement.³¹ This distinction would also have practical implications for the obstructive and destructive uses. If such uses do not qualify as prohibited uses of force (as discussed in Section 3.3 below), it would be important to clarify whether recourse can be had to “peaceful purposes” as a standalone obligation for regulating such uses and addressing any resulting harm to human life and well-being.

3.2. Nuclear Weapons and Weapons of Mass Destruction

Article IV of the OST provides that no objects carrying nuclear weapons or weapons of mass destruction (WMD) shall be placed into orbit, installed on celestial bodies, or stationed in outer space.³² EMP-generating nuclear systems would likely constitute nuclear weapons, whereas DEWs could only constitute WMDs if designed with “characteristics comparable in destructive effect to those of the atomic bomb or [atomic explosive weapons, radioactive material weapons, lethal chemical and biological weapons]”.³³ In 2003, Geis forecast that it would be unlikely that future forms of DEWs as at 2025 would constitute WMDs as “[m]icrowaves can be totally non-lethal, and both lasers and microwaves have beams that can be aimed to reduce the potential for collateral damage”.³⁴ Insofar as this is true of existing forms, DEWs would not fall within the OST prohibition, qualifying as conventional weapons rather than WMDs.

²⁸ Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. IV).

²⁹ *Ibid* (arts. IX, XI).

³⁰ Ortega, A. A., & Samson, V. *supra* note 20 (p. 34).

³¹ Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 275).

³² Outer Space Treaty, *supra* note 19 (art. IV).

³³ UN General Assembly. (December 12, 1977). *Prohibition of the development and manufacture of new types of weapons of mass destruction and new systems of such weapons*. A/RES/32/84-B. <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/623117?ln=en&v=pdf> (para. 3); *See, for example*, The International Campaign to Abolish Nuclear Weapons (ICAN). (n.d.). *What are space nuclear weapons?* ICAN. https://www.icanw.org/what_are_space_nuclear_weapons

³⁴ Geis, J. P. (2003). *Directed Energy Weapons on the Battlefield: A New Vision for 2025*. Center for Strategy and Technology, Air War College, Air University. <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/citations/ADA463429> (p. 39).

Even if future forms of DEWs were to qualify as WMDs or even as nuclear weapons, there is the question of whether such DEWs could nonetheless be employed in self-defence under the UN Charter. The ICJ has found that the lawfulness of nuclear weapons would be unclear “in an extreme circumstance of self-defence, in which the very survival of a State would be at stake”,³⁵ and Article 103 of the UN Charter provides that its obligations prevail over those of all other international agreements in the event of an incompatibility, which would include the OST.³⁶ While this question exceeds the limited scope of this paper, it is notable that there is no clear consensus. *The Woomera Manual on the International Law of Military Space Operations* (“Woomera Manual”), a non-binding manual prepared by leading experts on international law, space security, and other relevant areas, calls for the adoption of an “extremely nuanced approach” to this question.³⁷

As the OST is silent on the use of conventional weapons in void space, this gap in the governance of DEWs and their risks to human life and well-being would need to be otherwise addressed, such as by potentially establishing relevant protocols to the Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons. A similar conclusion can be drawn in respect of obstructive uses. As obstructive uses do not inherently or directly cause large-scale, irreversible, and physical damage, such uses would not be prohibited under the OST as WMDs, despite their potential cascading effects. The following sections will thus examine whether the obstructive and destructive uses and their risks to human life and well-being could instead be governed with reference to obligations related to *jus ad bellum*, harmful interference, and due regard.

3.3. Use of Force

Article 2(4) of the UN Charter prohibits the use of force, which has been interpreted by the International Court of Justice (ICJ) as applying “to any use of force, regardless of the weapons employed”.³⁸ Notwithstanding this expansive language, Article 41 of the UN Charter specifically provides that “measures not involving the use of armed force [...] may include complete or partial interruption of [...] radio, and other means of communication”.³⁹ Based on Article 41, together with State practice, it has been argued that jamming could not amount to a use of force.⁴⁰ However, this interpretation is not universally accepted. For example, Mountin argues that such an interpretation would be “overreaching” as “drafters of the Charter never contemplated satellite signal interference would be used to cause physical damage and human injury”,⁴¹ and Pobjie writes that “jamming and spoofing operations may constitute prohibited uses of force when they create sufficiently severe effects or target critical systems [...] even without direct physical damage to space systems or terrestrial harm”.⁴² Thus, while acknowledging the contested legal status of jamming, this Section 3.3 will proceed on the tentative presumption that each of the obstructive and destructive uses may constitute uses of force.

³⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (1996, July 8). *Legality of the Threat or Use of Nuclear Weapons* (Advisory Opinion) (para. 105(2)).

³⁶ *Charter of the United Nations*, opened for signature June 26 1945, 1 UNTS XVI (entered into force October 24 1945) (“UN Charter”) (art. 103).

³⁷ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (pp. 10–12).

³⁸ UN Charter, *supra* note 36 (art. 2(4)); International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 35 (para. 39).

³⁹ UN Charter, *supra* note 36 (art. 41).

⁴⁰ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 210); DeFabo, V. L. (2021). Rethinking Cyberspace Operations: Widespread Electromagnetic Jamming by States Indicates Cyber Interference Is Not a Use of Force. *Journal of Air Law and Commerce*. 86(2), 219–277. <https://scholar.smu.edu/jalc/vol86/iss2/3> (pp. 223, 250).

⁴¹ Mountin, S. M. (2014). The Legality and Implications of Intentional Interference with Commercial Communication Satellite Signals. *International Law Studies*. 90, 103–197. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1013&context=ils> (p. 192).

⁴² Pobjie, E. (2025). Cosmic Force: A Framework for Applying the Prohibition of the Use of Force in Outer Space. *International Law Studies*. 106, 415–454. <https://digital-commons.usnwc.edu/ils/vol106/iss1/13/> (p. 452).

There is no settled definition of a use of force, but it is traditionally understood as involving (1) kinetic means, (2) severe, permanent physical effects, (3) a causal link between the means and effects, and (4) a coercive or hostile intent.⁴³ There can be a mismatch between these traditional elements and contemporary challenges, as highlighted in the Tallinn Manual, which describes the *lex lata* of *jus ad bellum* (among other areas of law) as applied to cyber operations, as well as recent consensus-building efforts on the application of international law in cyberspace. These include the efforts of the UN Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) and UN Open Ended Working Groups (OEWGs) on ICT security, for which position papers were submitted, which may potentially contribute to the development of customary international law (namely, *opinio juris*). While recognising cyberspace and the EMS as imperfect analogues, this Section 3.3 will refer to the Tallinn Manual and GGE and OEWG position papers for the purpose of assessing the potential application of emerging approaches to *jus ad bellum* in relation to the obstructive and destructive uses.

As enumerated above, the first traditional element of a use of force is the employment of kinetic means, contrary to the obstructive and destructive uses, which are non-kinetic means. States have stated in GGE and OEWG position papers that non-kinetic cyber operations may constitute uses of force where the scale and effects are comparable to those of traditional, kinetic uses of force⁴⁴ (even though “scale and effects” have traditionally referred to ‘armed attacks’ rather than uses of force⁴⁵). This reflects an increasing openness to non-kinetic means as uses of force, although such openness is more evident in a cyber context than in an EMS-context, as noted in the Woomera Manual:

⁴³ See, for example, Kilovaty, I. (2014). Cyber Warfare and the Jus Ad Bellum Challenges: Evaluation in the Light of the Tallinn Manual on the International Law Applicable to Cyber Warfare. *American University National Security Law Brief*, 5(1), 91–124. <https://digitalcommons.wcl.american.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?referer=&httpsredir=1&article=1066&context=nslb>;

Pobjie, E. (2024). Elements of ‘Use of Force’: Effects, Gravity and Intention. In *Prohibited Force: The Meaning of ‘Use of Force’ in International Law*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009022897.010> (pp. 132–158).

⁴⁴ Australian Government. (2018). *Australia’s submission on international law to be annexed to the report of the 2021 Group of Governmental Experts on Cyber*. NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence (CCDCOE). https://ccdcoc.org/uploads/2018/10/Australia_submission-on-international-law-to-be-annexed-to-the-report-of-the-2021-Group-of-Governmental-Experts-on-Cyber.pdf (p. 2); Republic of Austria. (2024, April). *Position Paper of the Republic of Austria: Cyber Activities and International Law*. UN Office for Disarmament Affairs. [https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Austrian_Position_Paper_-_Cyber_Activities_and_International_Law_\(Final_23.04.2024\).pdf](https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Austrian_Position_Paper_-_Cyber_Activities_and_International_Law_(Final_23.04.2024).pdf) (p. 6);

Republic of Costa Rica. (2021). *Costa Rica’s Position on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. UN Office for Disarmament Affairs. https://docs-library.unoda.org/Open-Ended_Working_Group_on_Information_and_Communication_Technologies_-_2021/Costa_Rica_-_Position_Paper_-_International_Law_in_Cyberspace.pdf (p. 11); Kjelgaard, J. M., & Melgaard, U. (2023). Denmark’s Position Paper on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace: Introduction. *Nordic Journal of International Law*, 92(3), 446–455. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718107-20230001> (p. 451); Kingdom of Thailand. (2025, July). *Thailand’s National Position on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Kingdom of Thailand. https://image.mfa.go.th/mfa/0/6p4M7ae5k9/Thailands_NP_JUL2025_.pdf (p. 6); Government of Czech Republic. (2024). *Position paper on the application of international law in cyberspace*. Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Czech Republic. https://mzv.gov.cz/file/5376858/20240226_CZ_Position_paper_on_the_application_of_IL_cyberspace.pdf (p. 8); Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade. (2023, July). *Position Paper on the Application of International Law in Cyberspace*. Government of Ireland. <https://www.dfa.ie/media/dfa/ourrolepolicies/internationallaw/Ireland---National-Position-Paper.pdf> (para. 18).

⁴⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (1986, June 26). *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and against Nicaragua (Nicaragua v. United States of America)* (Judgment) (para. 195); Tallinn Manual, *supra* note 21 (p. 331).

“Unlike potential use of cyber capabilities [...] the potential use of non-kinetic capabilities along the electromagnetic spectrum as weapons in space is a developing area that some States are not yet prepared to [consider] may constitute a use of force.”⁴⁶

The second traditional element concerns severe, permanent physical effects such as death, injury, damage, or destruction. Destructive uses align with this traditional approach as such uses can permanently damage satellites (in the case of third-order risks) and terrestrial electronics (in the case of second-order risks), whereas obstructive uses merely interfere with satellite signals without causing physical damage. If interferences occur repeatedly, frequently, or for a long duration, and affect critical infrastructure (e.g., the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), which is integral for power grids and crop management systems),⁴⁷ obstructive uses could indirectly cause deaths on Earth (in the case of third-order risks). However, it is unclear whether such cascading effects resulting in deaths would be sufficient for qualifying obstructive uses as uses of force.

Some GGE and OEWG position papers reflect an expansive interpretation of “effects”, recognising the loss of functionality of critical infrastructure alongside death, injury, damage, and destruction, although not all such States recognise the temporary or reversible loss of functionality.⁴⁸ Accordingly, obstructive uses undermining critical infrastructure could potentially qualify as prohibited uses of force, unless it is necessary that the effects are permanent. As noted in the Woomera Manual, it is arguable that even temporary interferences against “satellites that provide an early warning of nuclear ballistic missile launches” and related systems could qualify as uses of force, given that this would pose a grave threat to international peace and security.⁴⁹

The third traditional element concerns the causal relationship between the means and the effects. Although the UN Charter does not contain express requirements to establish causation, this may reflect the fact that causation is relatively straightforward for kinetic means compared with non-kinetic ones. Consider an example of third-order risks, involving a jamming attack against a constellation of dual-use satellites for monitoring agriculture and optimising crop yields, which exacerbates an existing famine and results in thousands of people losing their lives over the course of several months. Such effects would not be as immediate or direct as in the simpler, more traditional scenario of one person shooting another person with a gun.

Urs examines three possible standards of causation in the context of cyber operations: (1) a “sufficiently direct and certain causal nexus”, (2) “effects that are proximate in space and time” rather than remote, and

⁴⁶ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 213).

⁴⁷ See, for example, Tryb J., & Hospodka, J. (2025). GNSS Interference and Security: Impacts on Critical Infrastructure and Mitigation Strategies. *Procedia Computer Science*. 253, 2635–2644. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.01.323> (p. 2636–2637); Solms, T. (2025, May 5). Securing the skies: tackling the growing threat of GPS interference. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/securing-the-skies-tackling-the-growing-threat-of-gps-interference/>; International Telecommunications Union (ITU). (2025, March 26). UN agencies warn of satellite navigation jamming and spoofing. *ITU*. <https://www.itu.int/hub/2025/03/un-agencies-warn-of-satellite-navigation-jamming-and-spoofing/>; Pashby, T. (2025, July 14). Plans to boost critical infrastructure resilience to GPS jamming agreed between UK and France. *New Civil Engineer*. <https://www.newcivilengineer.com/latest/plans-to-boost-critical-infrastructure-resilience-to-gps-jamming-agreed-between-uk-and-france-14-07-2025/>

⁴⁸ Australian Government, *supra* note 44; Republic of Costa Rica, *supra* note 44; Kingdom of Thailand, *supra* note 44.

⁴⁹ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (p. 220).

(3) reasonably foreseeable effects.⁵⁰ Applied to the above example, the first standard would not be satisfied because the effects of the jamming attack are indirect. The second standard is relatively flexible, but it is arguable that – although a thorough, case-by-case assessment would be required in practice – the effects are not proximate in either space (i.e., outer space versus Earth) or time (i.e., several months have passed). The longer the delay between the means and effects, the more likely it is that intervening factors have broken the chain of causation. Pursuant to the third standard, it could also be argued that the perpetrator of the jamming attack could not have reasonably foreseen that the dual-use satellites served critical applications upon which lives depended. As Kuplic and Sawmiller illustrate in the following hypothetical scenario, the uses of satellites can be difficult to ascertain:

“The decision to begin jamming is based on signals intelligence indicating that the enemy communications ministry leases some frequencies on that transponder and the enemy air force uses those frequencies to command and control armed unmanned aerial vehicles. Intelligence reporting also indicates that some frequencies on the same transponder are leased from the satellite operator BigSatCo by a commercial communications company, GlobalCommCo, which subcontracts with a second commercial communications company, RegionalCommCo, which in turn contracts with any users in the transponder footprint willing to pay for its voice and data transmission services. Such arrangements are common in the modern world of ever-increasing commercialization of space services.”⁵¹

Establishing causation would be less complex in the case of second-order risks, but challenges remain. Consider an EMP in outer space resulting in a two-year power outage on Earth. Bearing in mind the criticality of power for basic human needs, many lives would be lost, but not immediately. The third standard of causation could be satisfied as the destructive effects of an EMP (if caused deliberately) are reasonably foreseeable, even if the precise scale and effects could not be foreseen. However, the other two standards could not be satisfied, as the causal relationship remains indirect, and it is unclear whether harm occurring over a two-year time span would be considered sufficiently proximate.

The fourth traditional element concerns a coercive or hostile intent. Despite the material risks of obstructive and destructive uses to human life and well-being, it would follow that such uses may not constitute prohibited uses of force where the actor was well-intentioned. For example, a commercial actor testing a high-energy laser for removing orbital debris might accidentally strike a functioning satellite, or a spacecraft running on a nuclear power source might accidentally generate an EMP. Such accidents are not unlikely in an inherently high-risk and accident-prone environment such as outer space. Thus, if *jus ad bellum* were inapplicable, it would be important to have recourse to other regimes to ensure that any resulting risks to human life and well-being do not escape regulation.

However, Pobjie and Ortega write that the elements of a use of force are subject to a balancing exercise, such that “a hostile or coercive intent may turn a forcible act into a use of force even if [...] the effects are temporary and reversible”.⁵² Accordingly, the doctrinal ambiguities discussed in this Section 3.3 (e.g., whether temporary, reversible effects of obstructive uses are recognised ‘effects’) would not necessarily

⁵⁰ Urs, P. (2023, April 25). The Causal Question in the Application of the Law on the Use of Force to Cyber Operations. *Centre for International Law, National University of Singapore*. <https://cil.nus.edu.sg/blogs/the-causal-question-in-the-application-of-the-law-on-the-use-of-force-to-cyber-operations/>

⁵¹ Kuplic, G. B., & Sawmiller, J. (2025). Humanity on the final frontier: Challenges in applying international humanitarian law to modern military. *International Review of the Red Cross*. 107(928), 200–237. space operations. <https://international-review.icrc.org/articles/humanity-on-the-final-frontier-928> (p. 233).

⁵² Pobjie, E. & Ortega, A. A. (2024, September). Space Security Legal Primer 1 – Outer Space & Use of Force. *UNIDIR*. <https://doi.org/10.37559/WMD/24/Space/02> (p. 25).

bar the finding that there exists a prohibited use of force. For example, obstructive or destructive uses occurring by accident may nonetheless qualify as prohibited uses of force if, on balance, the lack of intent is outweighed by the severity of the effects. A toolkit assessing hypothetical scenarios, such as the Cyber Law Toolkit on the intersection between international law and cyber operations,⁵³ would be helpful in demonstrating how such a balancing exercise could be operationalised in practice. (It is notable that a toolkit on the intersection between international law and counter-space and electromagnetic operations would additionally offer value in clarifying all doctrinal ambiguities discussed throughout this paper.)

3.4. Right of Self-Defence

Pursuant to Article 51 of the UN Charter and customary international law, an exception to the prohibition on the use of force is self-defence.⁵⁴ In the *Nicaragua* judgement, the ICJ provides that an ‘armed attack’, which triggers the right of self-defence, can be understood as a grave form of use of force with reference to scale and effects.⁵⁵ The ICJ excluded “mere frontier incident[s]” from the meaning of an armed attack,⁵⁶ while leaving the door open to the “mining of a single military vessel” in the *Oil Platforms* judgment,⁵⁷ reflecting that the threshold for an armed attack may vary depending on prevailing circumstances. For example, Schaller writes that damage to a submarine cable could constitute a grave use of force for a small island State, but not for a State with redundant cable infrastructure.⁵⁸ By analogy, an obstructive or destructive use against a satellite constellation used by several States for monitoring natural disasters could be construed as an armed attack by a disaster-prone State, but not by other States.

As a practical matter, the nuanced nature of the ‘scale and effects’ test risks generating uncertainty among States as to the circumstances under which the right of self-defence may be lawfully exercised, with States such as the US even maintaining that any use of force may trigger the right of self-defence.⁵⁹ This uncertainty would be further compounded in the context of the obstructive and destructive uses, where difficulties in forecasting effects, especially those which are indirect and long-term (as discussed in Section 3.3 above), would undermine the capacity of States to operationalise the test through *ex ante* assessments.

The lawful exercise of (individual) self-defence further requires that the relevant State be the victim of an armed attack.⁶⁰ However, the victim State can be unclear where the affected satellite was operated, owned, leased, or registered by several States. As highlighted in the Woomera Manual, if State A leases or otherwise relies on the services of a satellite that is registered with State B, it is possible that State A could not act in self-defence against a third State absent a genuine legal connection with that satellite.⁶¹ Even if the victim State could be identified, attributing the obstructive and destructive uses to the aggressor State can raise practical difficulties due to the relative absence of traceable markers compared

⁵³ See, Mačák, K., Minárik, T., & Jančárková, T. (Eds.). (2019-). *Cyber Law Toolkit*. (NATO Cooperative Cyber Defence Centre of Excellence).

⁵⁴ UN Charter, *supra note* 36 (art. 51); International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 176).

⁵⁵ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (paras. 191, 195).

⁵⁶ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 195).

⁵⁷ International Court of Justice (ICJ). (2003, November 6). *Oil Platforms (Islamic Republic of Iran v. United States of America)* (Judgment) (para. 72).

⁵⁸ Schaller, C. (2025, April 16). Attacks on Submarine Cables and Pipelines: A Self-Defence Approach Complementary to Law Enforcement. *EJIL:Talk!* <https://www.ejiltalk.org/attacks-on-submarine-cables-and-pipelines-a-self-defence-approach-complementary-to-law-enforcement/>

⁵⁹ Kuplic & Sawmiller, *supra note* 51 at 214.

⁶⁰ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra note* 45 (para. 195).

⁶¹ Woomera Manual, *supra note* 7 (pp. 235–236).

to kinetic counter-space capabilities (e.g., ASAT weapons).⁶² This would be detrimental for the victim State upon which the burden of proof in demonstrating the existence of the armed attack rests.⁶³

The right of self-defence is also subject to conditions of necessity and proportionality,⁶⁴ which Kretzmer describes as involving an assessment of “whether the force used was necessary to achieve legitimate ends of self-defence”, where “[m]eans can only be proportionate when they are necessary to achieve the legitimate ends.”⁶⁵ By way of illustration, suppose State A launches an armed attack against State B, involving GPS-guided missile strikes. State B may determine that launching interceptor missiles or employing DEWs to damage GPS satellites would not be strictly necessary if jamming or spoofing GPS signals could achieve the same legitimate end of repelling the attack. It may be considered that obstructive uses are relatively limited in scale and intensity given their temporary, reversible, and non-kinetic nature, whereas destructive uses would permanently deny State A (and potentially, third-party States) the constructive uses of the affected GPS satellites and generate space debris. In conducting such an assessment, however, State B would need to take due precautions as not to underestimate the indirect, long-term effects of the obstructive uses. For example, in 2025, GPS jamming amid the Israel-Iran war was suspected as a possible cause for a collision between two oil tankers in the Gulf of Oman,⁶⁶ underscoring the potential cascading effects of obstructive uses, which pose a threat to human life.

3.5. Harmful Interference

A “harmful interference” concerns an “interference which endangers the functioning of a radionavigation service or of other safety services or seriously degrades, obstructs, or repeatedly interrupts a radiocommunication service [...]”⁶⁷ under international telecommunications law. The term has been described as having a broader scope of meaning under international space law, also encompassing physical means of interference.⁶⁸ Thus, both the obstructive and destructive uses would likely fall within the scope of Article IX of the OST, whereas only the former would be covered under international telecommunications law.

International telecommunications law warrants brief discussion given the mandate of the ITU to “promote the adoption of measures for ensuring the safety of life through the cooperation of telecommunication services”.⁶⁹ Notably, Article 45 of the ITU Constitution contains a duty to avoid harmful interference to the radio communications of other States, and No. 15.1 of the Radio Regulations prohibits jamming.⁷⁰ However, the ITU Constitution further provides that “Member States retain their entire freedom with regard to military radio installations”, and military radio installations are subject to a far softer duty to

⁶² See Pobjie, *supra* note 42 (p. 426).

⁶³ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 57 (para. 57).

⁶⁴ International Court of Justice (ICJ), *supra* note 45 (paras. 194, 237).

⁶⁵ Kretzmer, D. (2013). The Inherent Right to Self-Defence and Proportionality in *Jus Ad Bellum*. *The European Journal of International Law*. 24(1). 235–282. doi: 10.1093/ejil/chs087 (p. 239).

⁶⁶ Mahle, M. M. (2025, July 2). GPS Jamming during Israel-Iran War Demonstrates Risks to Civilian Operations. *StepToe LLP*. <https://www.steptoelaw.com/en/news-publications/stepwise-risk-outlook/gps-jamming-during-israel-iran-war-demonstrates-risks-to-civilian-operations.html>

⁶⁷ International Telecommunications Union. (2024). *Radio Regulations*. <https://www.itu.int/pub/R-REG-RR> (“Radio Regulations”) (no. 1.169).

⁶⁸ Woomera Manual, *supra* note 7 (pp. 178–180); International Telecommunications Union (ITU). (last updated 2025, January). *Radio Interference*. ITU. <https://www.itu.int/en/mediacentre/backgrounders/Pages/radio-interference.aspx>

⁶⁹ *Constitution and Convention of the International Telecommunication Union*, opened for signature December 22, 1992, 1825 UNTS 1826 (entered into force July 1 1994) (“ITU Constitution”) (art. 1(2)(g)).

⁷⁰ *Ibid* (art. 45); International Telecommunications Union, *supra* note 67 (no. 15.1).

take measures to prevent harmful interference “so far as possible”.⁷¹ Thus, while these provisions govern obstructive uses, any such uses carried out in a military capacity escape coverage. Further, compliance with these provisions relies upon the good faith cooperation of States absent an enforcement mechanism within the ITU, and efforts by the ITU to persuade governments to stop jamming have often been unsuccessful in practice.⁷²

Meanwhile, Article IX of the OST imposes a duty onto States Parties to “undertake appropriate international consultations before proceeding with any such activity or experiment” which is believed to “cause potentially harmful interference with activities of other States Parties in the peaceful exploration and use of outer space”.⁷³ A duty to consult is far weaker than a duty to avoid harmful interference, and said duty to consult is only limited to activities in the “peaceful” use of outer space, such that it has been argued that no such duty exists in relation to interferences with satellite signals employed in the unlawful use (or threat) of force.⁷⁴ Thus, at present, the above duties related to harmful interference likely could not be relied upon to effectively address the risks flowing from the obstructive or destructive uses to human life and well-being.

3.6. Due Regard

Article IX of the OST provides that States Parties shall conduct space activities “with due regard to the corresponding interests of all other States Parties to the Treaty”.⁷⁵ The meaning of “due regard” is unsettled, but scholars have generally favoured a broad interpretation, which would encompass obstructive and destructive uses that undermine the freedom of use of outer space as enjoyed by other States.⁷⁶

While the seas and outer space are imperfect analogues, this Section 3.6 adopts the view of the Republic of the Philippines, which wrote in its 2022 submission to the UN General Assembly that the interpretation of the due regard obligation within the law of the sea regime “could offer practical guidance in the context of clarifying the application of the same duty in outer space”.⁷⁷ For example, the Tribunal in the *Chagos Marine Protected Area Arbitration* case refers to the due regard obligation as “functionally equivalent” to the requirement to “refrain from unjustifiable interference”.⁷⁸ Further, the Tribunal provides that:

“[T]he extent of the regard required by the [UN Convention on the Law of the Sea] will depend upon the nature of the rights held by [the affected State], their importance, the extent of the anticipated impairment, the nature and importance of

⁷¹ ITU Constitution, *supra note* 69 (art. 48).

⁷² See, for example, International Telecommunications Union (ITU), *supra note* 47; de Selding, P. B. (2010, January 8). France Seeks ITU Help To Halt Satellite Signal Jamming by Iran. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/france-seeks-itu-help-halt-satellite-signal-jamming-iran/>; de Selding, P. B. (2010, March 26). ITU Implores Iran To Help Stop Jamming. *Space News*. <https://spacenews.com/itu-implores-iran-help-stop-jamming/>

⁷³ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note* 19 (art. IX).

⁷⁴ Mountin, *supra note* 41 (pp. 152–153).

⁷⁵ Outer Space Treaty, *supra note* 19 (art. IX).

⁷⁶ Jarose, J. (2023). Giving Due Regard to the Obligation of ‘Due Regard’ Under Article IX of the Outer Space Treaty. *Melbourne Journal of International Law*. 24(2), 1–25 https://law.unimelb.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0009/5034708/Jarose-Advance-Copy.pdf (p. 3); Kuplic & Sawmiller, *supra note* 51.

⁷⁷ Republic of the Philippines. (2022). *The duty of “due regard” as a foundational principle of responsible behavior in space* (UN General Assembly, UN Doc A/AC.294/2022/WP); <https://documents.unoda.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/Philippines-Due-Regard-Paper.pdf> (para. 11).

⁷⁸ Permanent Court of Arbitration. (2015). *Chagos Marine Protected Area Arbitration (Mauritius v United Kingdom)*: Award of 18 March 2015. <https://pca-epa.org/en/cases/11/> (p. 540).

the activities contemplated by the [responsible State], and the availability of alternative approaches.”⁷⁹

A similar balancing exercise could be undertaken in respect of the obstructive and destructive uses. For example, if an obstructive or destructive use carried out by State A is expected to impair the right of State B to use outer space (e.g., by denying State B access to constructive uses), then it must be the case that no or few reasonable alternatives existed, and the obstructive or destructive use was of such a nature or degree of importance as to justify the interference. Otherwise, a violation of the due regard obligation can be established.

Chen considers that there is no justifiable reason for intentionally jamming or spoofing, such that the due regard obligation is tantamount to a prohibition of such acts.⁸⁰ Further, bearing in mind the third-order risks of the destructive uses in permanently damaging satellites and denying States of their constructive uses, as well as the resulting generation of space debris that could further damage other satellites, the destructive uses are also likely to violate the due regard obligation. Thus, given its breadth of scope, the due regard obligation warrants particular examination as a possible means for governing both the obstructive and destructive uses.

4. CONCLUSION

This paper has sought to identify legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities in the application of the existing international space law framework, including *jus ad bellum*, to the obstructive and destructive uses. In particular, it is unclear whether such uses constitute space activities for the purposes of the OST amid ongoing spatialism-functionalism debates, and the classification of obstructive uses as prohibited uses of force is contested, given their non-traditional characteristics (e.g., temporary, reversible, non-physical effects) and Article 41 of the UN Charter. Even where obstructive and destructive uses qualify as prohibited uses of force, uncertainties remain concerning the applicable standard of causation, the relevance of indirect or long-term effects, and the weight of each element, including a coercive or hostile intent. Further, there are possible tensions between international space law and *jus ad bellum*, such as the question of whether the right of self-defence could prevail over the OST rules on prohibited weapons under Article 103 of the UN Charter.

The obstructive and destructive uses can undermine the constructive uses, thereby posing risks to human life and well-being. As reliance on satellite systems and their constructive uses accelerates worldwide, managing these risks is increasingly relevant for disaster preparedness, critical infrastructure resilience, and international legal governance, requiring the careful examination of applicable legal frameworks. Thus, it is essential to clarify and address existing legal lacunae to ensure the governance of the obstructive and destructive uses, with a view to regulating and protecting satellite systems, their constructive uses, and the lives they support. This paper has highlighted the potential role of the due regard obligation of international space law for governing the obstructive and destructive uses given its breadth in scope, as well as the possibility of prohibiting obstructive uses falling short of prohibited uses of force by resorting instead to the “peaceful purposes” requirement of the OST.

Thus, this paper calls for further research, policy discussions, and consensus-building efforts to address existing legal lacunae in respect of the application of the international space law framework to the obstructive and destructive uses. State position papers (e.g., as part of GGE and OEWG), expert manuals (e.g., Tallinn Manual, Woomera Manual), and toolkits assessing hypothetical scenarios (e.g., Cyber Law

⁷⁹ *Ibid* (para. 519).

⁸⁰ Chen, K.-W. (2024). *Legal Implications of Intentional Interference with Space Signals*. (Centre for Space, Cyberspace & Data Law; No. 2). Bond University. <https://bond.edu.au/research/research-centres-and-institute/centre-for-space-cyberspace-and-data-law> (pp. 1–18).

Toolkit) have contributed to the clarification of applicable legal frameworks to cyber operations and counter-space operations, and may similarly assist in clarifying how international law applies to the specific nexus between outer space and the EMS, as exemplified by the obstructive and destructive uses.

Due to its limited scope, this paper is inexhaustive in examining the rules and principles of international space law and *jus ad bellum* of potential relevance (e.g., outer space as a province of all mankind, threat of force). Further, while the categories of the ‘constructive’, ‘obstructive’, and ‘destructive’ uses are considered in this paper, specific uses of the EMS in outer space (e.g., jamming versus spoofing) additionally warrant individual examination owing to each of their unique characteristics. It is also notable that some legal lacunae and doctrinal ambiguities discussed in this paper may be resolved over time with the emergence of customary international law, or filled with recourse to rules and principles of general international law (e.g., non-intervention principle, laws of State responsibility), other specialised areas of public international law (e.g., international humanitarian law, international telecommunications law, international environmental law), or national laws, each of which also warrant further examination.